

ULTRASONIC DISPERSION AND ABSORPTION IN CURING EPOXY

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Abstract

We present the results of ultrasonic spectroscopy of a curing epoxy resin system, Epon 815/V-140. A 50 °C cure was monitored by launching broad-band ultrasonic pulses through the material and observing the frequency-dependent velocity dispersion and amplitude absorption. Results are analyzed based on the molecular theory of visco-thermal absorption, coupled with the segmental relaxation processes possible in polymeric systems. The latter, coupled with dielectric spectroscopy and dynamic mechanical analysis would represent a complete decomposition of the complicated glass transition behavior that controls the epoxy's resulting performance quality. It is concluded that several segmental relaxation processes occur at changing characteristic frequency prior to gelation and at constant frequency after gelation. This information is pertinent for ultrasonic spectroscopy of epoxy matrix composites in that absorption peaks from multiple scattering of fibers and voids are accompanied by absorption peaks from molecular processes. An understanding of the latter is necessary to correctly interpret absorption with contributions from both sources.

KEYWORDS: absorption; dynamic response; matrix epoxy; ultrasonic; sensor

1. Introduction

Structural relaxation of a material is a process in which the material rearranges itself under the influence of various perturbations. Several modes of relaxation exist for polymer systems, with each mode being characterized by a time τ , and an appropriate scaling form. Examples include reptation, kink formation, and rotational isomerism. In ultrasonic spectroscopy, the latter is dominant and leads to peaks in absorption per wavelength ($\mu = \alpha\lambda$). When τ is much larger than the

perturbation or observation times, the material behaves as a glass (well below the T_g). Conversely, for perturbation times much larger than τ , the material behaves as a liquid (well above the T_g). In comparison to quiescent thermal analysis, probing the material with varying frequency has the benefit of separating different modes of relaxation, providing the ability to understand the glass transition at a molecular level.

2. Theory

In general, an ultrasonic wave is accompanied by a thermal wave. In polymers, the local temperature fluctuations are thought to promote and demote the side-chain substituents between stable and unstable states through rotational isomeric spinning. As the perturbation time approaches the relaxation time, the material does not have time to equilibrate, so work is done on the material. In this case, the pulse loses more energy at frequencies near $1/\tau$ than that predicted by visco-thermal absorption¹. Researchers usually introduce a complex heat capacity to explain this phenomena²:

$$C_v^\omega = C_{v\infty} + \frac{C_i}{1 + i\omega\tau} \quad (1)$$

With such a form, the thermal wave is predicted to be thrown out of phase with the stress wave, leading to destructive 'interference' and energy loss, in the region $\omega\tau \approx 1$. Accounting for this complex heat capacity, the absorption has been calculated to be²:

$$\frac{\alpha}{f^2} = \frac{\alpha_{vt}}{f^2} + \frac{2\pi^2}{U_o} \frac{R' C_i}{C_v (C_p - C_i)} \frac{\tau'}{1 + \omega^2 \tau'^2} \quad (2)$$

where $R' = (C_p - C_v)$, U_o is the low shear rate phase velocity, and α_{vt} is the visco-thermal absorption, shown in equation (3).

$$\alpha_{vt} = \frac{2\pi^2}{\rho U^3} \left[\frac{4}{3} \eta_s + \eta_B + \frac{\gamma - 1}{\gamma} \frac{\kappa}{C_v} \right] f^2 \quad (3)$$

It is also convenient to introduce the absorption per wavelength:

$$\mu_{relax} = \frac{U^2}{U_o^2} \frac{\pi R' C_i}{C_v (C_p - C_i)} \frac{\omega\tau'}{1 + \omega^2 \tau'^2} \quad (4)$$

This term, combined with (2) leads to the total absorption per wavelength,

$$\mu_{TOTAL} = \mu_{vt} + B \frac{U^2 \omega \tau_1}{1 + \omega^2 \tau_1^2} + C \frac{U^2 \omega \tau_2}{1 + \omega^2 \tau_2^2} + \dots \quad (5)$$

Neglecting the small effect of velocity dispersion, this equation predicts that the relaxation peaks will have half-height widths of:

$$\frac{\Delta\omega_1}{2} = 2\sqrt{3}\omega \quad (6)$$

For example, the width for a relaxation process at 5 MHz is predicted to be 17 MHz. As we will later show, this restriction limits the ability to predict the observed absorption spectra. We decided to generalize the relaxation formulae to a form which we could explain the sharper absorption peaks observed. With the generalized form, we have,

$$\mu = \mu_{vt} + Bf(\omega\tau_1) + Cf(\omega\tau_2) + \dots \quad (7)$$

where,

$$f(\omega\tau) = \frac{2}{e^{(\beta \ln(\omega\tau))} + e^{-(\beta \ln(\omega\tau))}} \quad (8)$$

a form suggested in the dielectric spectroscopy literature^{3,4}. When $\beta = 1$, we have the Debye form of equation (4). In the data analysis section below, we explain the method used to determine the unknowns in equation (7).

3. Experimental Approach

3.1 Materials

Epon 815, a bisphenol-A epichlorohydrin type epoxy was mixed the curing agent, V-140 vigorously for 15 minutes. Stoichiometric quantities were used based on the functionality of the parts. Bubbles were formed during the mixing, but the sudden decrease in viscosity as the samples were added to the heat cell expedited their elimination.

3.2 Experimental Set-up

The experimental set-up for this study is discussed in detail elsewhere⁵. The set-up is shown in figure 1. It features an environmental chamber with a disk-shaped cavity and provision for a delay-line connection to the external transducer. The transducer was driven by a Panametrics 5052 wide-band pulser/receiver, and signals were retrieved via PC to a 100 MHz sampling oscilloscope.

Figure 1: Ultrasonic Cell

3.4 Data Analysis

3.4.1 Ultrasonic Signal Analysis

The geometry described above leads to the schematic of wave propagation shown in figure 2. Here, Z_i refers to the acoustic impedances of the materials (which, along with stress, control the reflectivity of the interface).

Figure 2: Schematic of Pulse-Echo Wave Travel (oblique wave vectors drawn for clarity only)

The phase velocity through the test material can be determined by measuring the frequency-dependent phase-lag between the transmitted pulse and the received pulse and using the formula,

$$v = \frac{\omega L}{(\phi - \phi_0)} \quad (8)$$

where ϕ is the phase of the signal at a certain frequency, ϕ_0 is a reference phase at that same frequency, and L is the thickness of the material traversed by the wave. We use the signal reflected from the delay-line/epoxy interface as the source for the reference phase.

The absorption coefficient is calculated using equation (9):

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{L} \ln \left(\frac{V_1}{V_2} \right) + \frac{1}{L} \ln \left(\frac{RC_{12}}{RC_{23}TC_{12}TC_{21}} \right) \quad (9)$$

where RC_{ij} and TC_{ij} are the reflection and transmission coefficients at the ij interfaces, respectively, and V's are the received signals shown in figure 1.

3.4.2 Absorption Spectra Correlation

The absorption-per-wavelength spectra were fitted with equation (7) using the least number of terms possible. First, the τ values for each peak were determined, following which the best β values for each peak were determined through regression on just the peak data. Finally, the coefficients A, B, and C were optimized for the best fit.

4. Results

Figures 3 and 4 show a sample signal in the time and frequency domains, respectively. Figures 5-8 show frequency plots of velocity, normalized absorption, and absorption per wavelength for four intermittent time during the cure. The plots show that as the cure proceeds, the frequency dependence of these variables changes dramatically. The results of modeling the absorption data with equation (7) are shown in figures 9-11. Since no strong absorption peak appeared in the 240 min. plot, these data were not modeled. We see that the model satisfactorily fits the data. For the 360 min. data, it was difficult to fit both peaks to our satisfaction, Although the correct trend is predicted. Table I summarized the parameters determined for this modeling.

Figure 12 shows the changing frequency dependence of the absorption-per-wavelength with time. It is seen that during the early stage of cure. The peak frequency is decreasing with time. After approximately 240 min., two new peak frequencies appear and stay fairly constant for the remainder of the cure. This is shown clearly in figure 13, where the peak frequencies are plotted versus time.

Table I: Modeling Parameters

Time	A	τ 1	beta 1	B	τ 2	beta 2	C
0 min	1.6- 1.6e-8w	2.3e-8	20.4	.44	N/A	N/A	N/A
120 min	1.474- 1.4e-8w	4.2e-8	6.8	1.07	N/A	N/A	N/A
360 min	3 - 5e-8w	2.8e-8	29.4	.72	1.5e-8	10.6	1.03

Figure 3: Sample Signal

Figure 4: Frequency-Domain of Sample Signal

Figure 5: 50 °C, 0 min.

Figure 6: 50 °C, 120 min.

Figure 7: 50 °C, 240 min.

Figure 8: 50 °C, 360 min

Figure 9: Modeling of 0 min. Data

Figure 10: Modeling of 120 min. Data

Figure 11: Modeling of 360 min. Data

Figure 12: Absorption vs. Time vs. Frequency for 50 °C Cure

Figure 13: Peak Frequency vs. Time

5. Discussion

Clearly, molecular relaxation is contributing to the absorption observed in our experiments. The sharpness of the absorption peaks is much greater than that observed in dilute solutions of linear polymers⁶, where beta values ~ 1 are applicable. The observed sharpness suggests a cooperative phenomenon between neighbors in the condensed phase, as well as possible rotational isomeric spin resonance.

Further work in this area will include an extension of the frequency and temperature range of the experiments. We plan to investigate the activation energy of the relaxation processes by finding the time and temperature dependences of τ . Knowing the activation energies would be helpful in identifying the chemical species involved in the relaxation process. Finally, we would like to identify physical meaning for the beta value used in equation (7).

6. Biography of Authors

Patrick Mather received his B.S. in Engineering Science in 1989 and M.S. in Engineering Mechanics in 1990 from Penn State University, where his advisor was Dr. H. Thomas Hahn. He is pursuing a PhD in Materials at the University of California at Santa Barbara, where he is studying the processing of liquid crystalline polymers.

Scott White earned a B.S in Mechanical Engineering in 1985 from University of Missouri at Rolla, an M.S. in Mechanical Engineering in 1987 from Washington University, and a PhD in Engineering Science and Mechanics in 1990 from Penn State University, where his advisor was Dr. H. Thomas Hahn. He is currently Assistant Professor of Aerospace and Aeronautical Engineering at the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign.

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